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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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I Have Something to Tell You

I have something to tell you.
You know what? I saw a post on Facebook today.
It said, "It is okay to do nothing after work," or so they say.
It made me feel like, "Oh, someone finally understands me."
But reality struck, asking, "Are you single? That post is for
the kid-free."
A moment later, I sighed, "Yeah, you are right."
Who am I to rest when they wait for me every night?
It isn't that I'm complaining, but then again, why not?
But I am a mother, and complain I must not.

You know what? I saw a post on Twitter, too.
It said, "You give so much in everything you do!"
I wish I were hearing this from someone dear,
But to them, "Rest is earned by paying your share."
Regardless of the thought, the words gave me a boost,
I only pray that in giving so much, I don't become lost.
Don't worry, I am well aware of my limitation,
My only fear? My dearest doesn't understand my situation.

You know what? I heard a beautiful song last night.
I even giggled, holding my pillow tight.
The lyrics asked, "Can we go back to the days our love was strong?"
I want to hear this from my dear, please don't get me wrong!
You might ask what part of the song made me shed a tear?
Simple. It sang the words that I have been longing to hear.
Please! Please! I am okay.
I still feel loved. Don't look at me that way.

You know what? Hey! This will be the last!
Please pay attention. I won't mention my dear, so you won't
be aghast.
Okay! Remember that guy from my past?
Yes! That one. He is coming back here at last!
I am so happy that he will return for good.

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The only thing that bothers me is my dear might misunderstand the mood.

But then again, I am still delighted by his homecoming!

Wait, what am I thinking?

I hope my dear doesn't hear what I am saying.

If so, the words he'll speak might leave my mind numbing.